

Probabilistic interpretation of elemental partitioning and diffusion in the presence of a phase interface

Aarne Pohjonen

Materials and mechanical engineering department, University of Oulu, Finland

E-mail: aarne.pohjonen@oulu.fi

Abstract. Random movement of atoms due to thermal fluctuations in material is the fundamental phenomena behind macroscopic diffusion. When the movement occurs in a regular crystal lattice, the random movement can be understood as a random walk of atoms in the lattice. In the previous study [1] we connected the theory between lattice random walk, activation energy for atom movement and macroscopic diffusion and examined few cases for bulk diffusion and precipitate growth. In the current study the lattice random walk simulation is applied for mathematically simulating elemental partitioning over an interface, a condition which is encountered in phase transformations in solid materials, e.g. in austenite decomposition to ferritic phases. The probability of atoms to move over the interface from one phase to another is connected to the macroscopic diffusive partitioning over the interface separating the two phases. Partitioning and diffusion over immobile as well as moving interface are considered.

1. Introduction

The fundamental physical phenomena in solid state diffusion is the movement of the diffusing atoms in the host material. In the case of crystalline solids, the moving atoms may assume interstitial or substitutional lattice position. While, in the case of interstitial diffusion, the diffusing atoms are almost always neighbored by vacant sites where to move, in substitutional diffusion atom can move from a lattice site to an equivalent site if there is a vacancy available in the neighbouring lattice site. [2]

While the diffusion mechanisms have differences in different cases, with complexity increasing from interstitial diffusion to substitutional atom diffusion to diffusion in amorphous materials, random walk models have been applied to describe the diffusion in each of these different cases [3, 4, 5].

The diffusion of carbon over austenite-ferrite interface is a technologically important topic which affects several mechanisms considered in recent articles [6, 7, 8, 9]. In these references the diffusion over the interface is considered only by macroscopic diffusion equations.

In the current article the focus is on the diffusion of interstitial atoms, where definitely the random walk models provide a direct description of the actual movement of atoms. The aim is to connect the probability of atom movement to the macroscopic diffusion equations. It is also noted that it is possible to estimate the rates (and hence the probability) from nudged elastic band method (NEB) from atomistic simulations [3]. Thus the random walk model and the probability of atom movement provide a fundamentally physical connection between the atomistic movement [10, 11] and the macroscopic diffusion equations used for example in [12, 13] and provide a scale-bridging understanding between these length scales. In particular the aim in

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the movement of atoms over given atomic plane and the crossing of activation energy barrier. Adapted from [3].

the current study is to consider the presence of a phase interface and its effect on the probability of atom movement over the interface on both sides of the interface. These probabilities are then theoretically linked to the macroscopic diffusion equations. Finally, some numerical experiments with random walk model are conducted to illustrate the model application in simple cases for immobile as well as for moving phase interface.

2. Theory

2.1. Probability and continuum descriptions of diffusion

In this study, the focus is on diffusion of interstitial atoms. The probability of atom movement p is thermally activated process and can be related to the diffusion coefficient and the associated kinetic energy barrier. If the kinetic energy of an interstitial atom overcomes certain threshold energy, the activation energy E_A , the atom surpasses the potential energy barrier for the movement from one lattice site to another. As is well known [2, 1], the thermally activated movement of atoms then leads to the diffusion process where the rate of atom movement Γ is related to the diffusion coefficient by $D = \frac{\Gamma a^2}{2N}$ where N is the dimension where diffusion occurs (i.e. $N = 2$ for two dimensional surface diffusion and $N = 3$ for usual diffusion in bulk), a is the lattice constant and $D = D_0 \exp(-E_A/RT)$ is the diffusion coefficient, which depends on temperature T . If the probability for atom movement is equal in each direction, the frequency of atom movement is related to the probability p for atom to move during a short time-interval by $\Gamma = Np/\Delta t$ [1].

Consider a plane with normal in x -direction, depicted in Fig. 1. If there are n_1 atoms on the negative side of the plane, that have probability p_{x1} to move over the plane to the positive side during time-interval Δt , and n_2 atoms on the positive side of the plane with probability p_{x2} to move over the plane to the negative direction, then the total flux in x -direction is

$$\vec{f}_x = \hat{n}_x \frac{(p_{x1}n_1 - p_{x2}n_2)}{A\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

For generality, let us consider unit cell widths a_1 and a_2 at left and right sides, respectively. Then $\vec{f}_x = \hat{n}_x [a_1 p_{x1} n_1 / (A a_1) - a_2 p_{x2} n_2 / (A a_2)] / \Delta t = \hat{n}_x [a_1 x_1 p_{x1} n_1 / V_1 - a_2 p_{x2} n_2 / V_2] / \Delta t$. Since the concentrations on the left and right sides of the plane are $C_1 = n_1 / V_1$ and $C_2 = n_2 / V_2$, the

flux can be expressed in terms of the concentrations

$$\vec{f}_x = \hat{n}_x [a_1 p_{x1} C_1 - a_2 p_{x2} C_2] / \Delta t \quad (2)$$

The similar expression holds for y and z directions, and the total flux $\vec{f} = \vec{f}_x + \vec{f}_y + \vec{f}_z$.

Consider the rate of change of concentration C in volume element Ω with volume V_Ω . Since the number concentration of atoms is conserved, the rate of concentration change $\partial_t C$ is described by Eq. (3)

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{V_\Omega} \int_{S_\Omega} \vec{f} \cdot \hat{n}_s ds \quad (3)$$

where S_Ω is the surface area of a small volume element Ω .

In the limit that the volume approaches zero, the integral in Eq. (3) approaches divergence and Fick's second law is obtained

$$\partial_t C = -\nabla \cdot \vec{f} = -(\partial_x f_x + \partial_y f_y + \partial_z f_z) \quad (4)$$

where the partial derivatives approximate the small change relative to distance. For x -direction

$$\partial_x f_x|_{x=x_0} \approx \frac{f_x(x_0 + \delta x/2) - f_x(x_0 - \delta x/2)}{\delta x}$$

and similarly for y - and z -directions.

2.2. Diffusion in homogeneous single phase

Before considering the presence of a phase interface, let us briefly review the probabilistic interpretation of bulk diffusion inside a single phase [1, 2]. For this purpose, assume a concentration field in a volume element contained within one phase, say α phase. When the plane is contained inside of a single homogeneous phase, the lattice constants and the probabilities for atom movement are equal at each side of the plane $a_1 = a = a_2$ and $p_{x1} = p_x = p_{x2}$, which yields $\vec{f}_x = -\hat{n}_x a p_x (C_2 - C_1) / \Delta t$. The change in concentration over the distance of lattice constant, a , can be obtained as $C_2 = C_1 + a \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$, which yields

$$\vec{f}_x = -\hat{n}_x D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

where $D = a^2 p / \Delta t = a^2 \Gamma / 6$ is the diffusion coefficient, $p = p_x = p_y = p_z$ for isotropic diffusion and Γ is the frequency of atom movement resulting from average probability. For isotropic three dimensional diffusion $\Gamma / 6 = p$ since there are 6 different directions for movement in three dimensional material. In general, for diffusion in N -dimensional cases $\Gamma / 2N = p_x$, where N is the dimension where the diffusion occurs [2].

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} &= -\frac{1}{V_\Omega} \int_{S_\Omega} \vec{f} \cdot \hat{n} ds \\ &= -\frac{1}{\delta x \delta y \delta z} ([f_x(x_0 + \delta x/2) - f_x(x_0 - \delta x/2)] \delta y \delta z + \\ &\quad [f_y(y_0 + \delta y/2) - f_y(y_0 - \delta y/2)] \delta x \delta z + \\ &\quad [f_z(z_0 + \delta z/2) - f_z(z_0 - \delta z/2)] \delta x \delta y) \\ &\approx -\nabla \cdot \vec{f} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the approximation becomes exact when $\lim \delta x \rightarrow 0 = \delta y \rightarrow 0 = \delta z \rightarrow 0 = 0$.

By applying Eq. (2) (e.g. $\vec{f}(x_0 + \delta x/2) = -\hat{n}_x ap(C(x_0 + \delta x) - C(x_0))/\Delta t$ and $\vec{f}(x_0 - \delta x/2) = -\hat{n}_x ap(C(x_0) - C(x_0 - \delta x))/\Delta t$), Eq. (6) can also be written using probability for atom movement and the concentrations at neighbouring sites as Eq. (7).

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} &= \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(x_0 + \delta x) - 2C(x_0) + C(x_0 - \delta x)) + \\
&\quad \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(y_0 + \delta y) - 2C(y_0) + C(y_0 - \delta y)) + \\
&\quad \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(z_0 + \delta z) - 2C(z_0) + C(z_0 - \delta z)) \\
&= \\
&\quad \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(x_0 + \delta x) - C(x_0)) + \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(x_0 - \delta x) - C(x_0)) + \\
&\quad \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(y_0 + \delta y) - C(y_0)) + \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(y_0 - \delta y) - C(y_0)) + \\
&\quad \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(z_0 + \delta z) - C(z_0)) + \frac{ap}{\Delta t} (C(z_0 - \delta z) - C(z_0))
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The Eq. (7) can be interpreted and applied in the following way: for each considered small rectangular (in 2d case) or cuboid region (in 3d) atoms can be transferred to the neighbouring regions corresponding to the movement probability p . This procedure provides a *rule* that can be applied for calculating diffusion in a very similar way as rules in cellular automata models for each position in computational grid [14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

2.3. Partitioning over immobile phase interface

Next, let us consider a volume element Ω with one face located at an immobile phase interface, which separates α and γ phases as depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Concentrations (C) and fluxes (\vec{f}) relevant for a volume element Ω located on the α - γ phase interface.

Consider rate of concentration change $\partial_t C_{i1}$ inside a volume element in α phase, directly on the left hand side of a phase interface with surface normal in x -direction, depicted in Fig. 2. To obtain the equation describing the rate, we need to calculate the flux of atoms over the surfaces of the volume element and then apply Eq. (3).

Consider first the flux of atoms over the facet, which is located on the phase interface. Assume probability p_{i1} of atom to move over the interface towards right during time interval Δt , adding to concentration C_{i2} on the right hand side of the interface, and probability p_{i2} for atom to move

over the interface from the right side to the left side. In reality, the unit cells at the interface may be distorted due to lattice mismatch between the two phases. However, to avoid the additional complexity, which likely has only minor effect on results, the unit cell of the Ω volume element will be considered the same as in the bulk α phase. The Eq. (2) yields total flux \vec{f}_i over the interface, Eq. (8).

$$\vec{f}_i = -\hat{n}_x(a_2p_{x2}C_{i2} - a_1p_{x1}C_{i1})/\Delta t \quad (8)$$

Consider then the flux of diffusing atoms to/from the volume element Ω over those faces where both sides are α phase. Since both phases are the same, these fluxes are bulk fluxes \vec{f}_b , and are described in the same way as in Eq. (5), which yields Eqs. (9, 10, 11).

$$\vec{f}_{b,x-} = -\hat{n}_x a_1 p_{x-} (C_{i1} - C_{1x-})/\Delta t = -\hat{n}_x D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}_- \quad (9)$$

$$\vec{f}_{b,y-} = -\hat{n}_y a_1 p_{y-} (C_{i1} - C_{1y-})/\Delta t = -\hat{n}_y D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}_- \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{f}_{b,y+} = \hat{n}_y a_1 p_{y+} (C_{i1} - C_{1y+})/\Delta t = \hat{n}_y D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}_+ \quad (11)$$

where + and - signs indicate derivative in positive/negative side of the considered position. The fluxes in z -direction are similar to the y direction. Once the fluxes are known from Eqs. (8, 9, 10, 11), the rate of change of concentration C_{i1} is given by Eq. (3) in the same way as in Eqs. (6, 7). In other words, the rate of change of concentration is obtained by calculating the divergence of fluxes, which yields Eq. (12).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{f_i - f_{b,x-}}{\delta x} + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

where f_i and $f_{b,x}$ are obtained from Eqs. (8) and (9).

If the gradient of the concentration field is zero in the y and z -directions at the considered point, then the fluxes $\vec{f}_{b,y-}$, $\vec{f}_{b,y+}$, $\vec{f}_{b,z-}$ and $\vec{f}_{b,z+}$ are zero. In this case only fluxes in x -direction remain and directly from Eq. (12), the rate of concentration change is described by Eq. (13).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{f_i - f_{b,x-}}{\delta x} \right) \quad (13)$$

where δx is the width of the region.

Let us now consider different steady state conditions for this case:

In the first type of steady state $\partial_t C = 0$. From Eqs. (13, 8) we obtain Eq. (14).

$$f_{b,x-} = f_i \iff D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}_- = (\delta x_2 p_{x2} C_{i2} - \delta x_1 p_{x1} C_{i1})/\Delta t \quad (14)$$

If, in addition, sufficient amount of time passes such that the concentration gradient is zero in the α and γ phases, then Eq. (15) holds. This is the second type of steady state.

$$f_i = 0 \iff \frac{C_{i1}}{C_{i2}} = \frac{\delta x_2 p_{x2}}{\delta x_1 p_{x1}} \quad (15)$$

In the third type of steady state, which we consider, the second order time derivative of the concentration is zero, i.e. $\partial_{tt} C = 0$. Let us assume for simplicity that p_{x1} , p_{x2} , δx_1 and δx_2 are independent of time. In this case we obtain Eq. (16)

$$\frac{\partial f_{b,x-}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial t} \iff \frac{\partial}{\partial t} D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_-} = \delta x_2 p_{x2} \frac{\partial C_{i2}}{\partial t} - \delta x_1 p_{x1} \frac{\partial C_{i1}}{\partial t} \quad (16)$$

Now, in the case that additionally $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} D_\alpha \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_-} = 0$, i.e. the gradient at the interface is approximately constant as function of time (i.e. the time-dependent change is very small and can be neglected), then

$$\frac{\partial_t C_{i1}}{\partial_t C_{i2}} = \frac{\delta x_2 p_{x2}}{\delta x_1 p_{x1}} \quad (17)$$

2.4. Partitioning over moving interface

Let us assume that a phase interface is moving with velocity \vec{v}_i . In the coordinate system where the moving interface is at origin (i.e. the coordinate system moves along with the interface) the concentration field moves in the opposite direction with velocity $\vec{v}_C = -\vec{v}_i$. The advection equation $\partial_t C = \nabla C \cdot (-\vec{v}_C)$ describes the translative movement of a field. At the same time as the interface moves, the atoms partition over the interface at both sides, as well as diffusion occurs within the phases.

Since the concentration is conserved, the continuity equation $\partial_t C = -\nabla \cdot \vec{f}$ describes the time evolution of the concentration field, where \vec{f} is the local flux, as defined in previous sections. Since partitioning and the phase interface movement occur simultaneously, the concentration can be described with advection-diffusion Eq. (18).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \vec{f} + \nabla C \cdot \vec{v}_i = -\nabla \cdot \vec{f} + \nabla C \cdot s \hat{n} \quad (18)$$

where $\vec{v}_i = s \hat{n}$ is the local velocity of the interface, s is the propagation speed in the interface normal \hat{n} direction.

For sharp or narrow interface model (narrow meaning that interface width is very small but non-zero) there can be discontinuity of the concentration field at the interface, and for this reason special consideration is needed to handle this type of situation. Consider the movement of the phase interface in the direction of positive x coordinate similar to shown in Fig. 2. For simplicity, let us assume that gradient is non-zero only in x -direction (i.e. in the direction of interface movement). In the case of sharp or narrow interface, in the coordinate system which is moving with the interface, at the leading side of the interface (coordinate x_{i2}), the evolution of the concentration at the interface can be calculated with Eq. (18) where the gradient ∇C is evaluated in the progressing (leading) side of the interface (at $x = x_{i2}$), which yields

$$C(x_{i2}, t + \Delta t) \approx C(x_{i2}, t_0) + \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i2}} s \Delta t - (\nabla \cdot \vec{f}) \Big|_{x=x_{i2}} \Delta t$$

where $(\nabla \cdot \vec{f})|_{x=x_{i2}} = -(f_i + f_{b,x+})/\delta x$, $f_i = a_2 p_{x2} C_{i2} - a_1 p_{x1} C_{i1}$ and $f_{b,x+} = -D_2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i2}}$, the gradient $\frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i2}}$ is evaluated at the positive side of the interface and D_2 is the diffusion constant at the leading side. Dividing both sides with Δt and taking limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ yields

$$\frac{\partial C_{i2}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i2}} s - (\nabla \cdot \vec{f}) \Big|_{x=x_{i2}}$$

At the trailing side of the phase interface (at coordinate $x = x_{i1}$) in the moving coordinate system, the concentration gradient is evaluated as $\partial_x C \Big|_{x=x_{i1}} = (C_{i2} - C_{i1})/\delta x_i$, where C_{i2} is

the concentration at the leading edge side of the interface, C_{i1} is the concentration at the trailing side of the interface, and δx_i is the interface width, which yields

$$\frac{\partial C_{i1}}{\partial t} = -(\nabla \cdot \vec{f}) \Big|_{x=x_{i1}} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i1}} s$$

where $(\nabla \cdot \vec{f})|_{x_{i1}} = (f_i - f_{b,x-})/\delta x$, $f_i = -(a_2 p_{x2} C_{i2} - a_1 p_{x1} C_{i1})/\Delta t$ and $f_{b,x-} = -D_1 \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_{i1}}$.

2.5. Random walk model

Since movement of individual atoms is considered in the random walk model, the interface position is considered as discrete, i.e. it is considered to exist at a given atomic plane which divides the region to two different phases. Although we do not consider atomic level interactions (such as could be done using atomistic simulations), this simple model captures certain atomic resolution effects such as fluctuations and the actual probabilities of atom movement are included in the calculation. On the other hand, the current random walk model is computationally inefficient in comparison to macroscopic diffusion models, and it is more difficult to incorporate the effect of local concentration to the movement of the phase interface, which can affect the movement over longer distances due to elastic stresses.

The overall implementation of the random walk model is quite simple and it is described in [1], but in the current study the focus is in the partitioning over the interface. In the presence of interface, the probabilities p_{x2} and p_{x1} in Eq. (8) need to be defined at the sites next to the interface. Once this is done, the random movement of atoms naturally yields the partitioning of the atoms. The method is straightforward to implement and it gives detailed description of the fluctuations and it can be in future linked to atomistic models, such as in [11, 10] by calculating activation energy barriers for atom movement [1], which then provide the rate and the probability.

3. Numerical experiments

In the following numerical experiments, the probability for atom movement was set as 0.25 to either left or right, when the atom was not located next to the interface. When the atom was located next to the interface, the probability to move from phase 1 to phase 2 was 0.7, and the probability for atom to move from phase 2 to phase 1 was set as 0.3. These values facilitated the atoms to partition over the interface from phase 1 to phase 2. Periodic boundaries were applied. The local concentrations were calculated by dividing the computational domain in to 40 subdomains in x -direction, and for each subdomain, the number of atoms in that domain is given.

3.1. Immobile interface

The Concentration of atoms after different time intervals in the presence of two immobile phase interfaces located at ± 100 lattice constants from origin is shown in Fig. 3. The phase closer to the origin was phase 1. The final condition of the simulation (1 000 000 time-steps) can be compared to the steady state case where the concentration gradient in each phase is zero. In this case from Eq. 15, where since $\delta x_1 = \delta x_2$ we obtain for the set probabilities $p_1 = 0.7$ and $p_2 = 0.3$ the fraction $C_{i1}/C_{i2} = p_2/p_1 = 0.3/0.7 \approx 0.4286$. From the random walk simulation (Fig. 3) we can see that the $C_{i1}/C_{i2} \approx 450/1050 \approx 0.4286$, which is the same value.

3.2. Moving interface

To consider the movement of an interface, the simulation was the same as in the previous case, but the right hand interface was set to move with velocity 0.01 lattice constants per time step.

Figure 3. Concentration of atoms after different time intervals in the presence of two immobile phase interfaces located at ± 100 lattice constants from origin. The result shows average values from 5 repeated simulations for each case. The error bars are the standard deviations of those simulations.

The concentration of atoms after different time intervals in the presence of the right moving phase interface is shown in Fig. 4 for different simulation time intervals. The result shows the occurrence of simultaneous partitioning, diffusion and phase interface propagation.

Figure 4. Concentration of atoms after different time intervals in the presence of two phase interfaces, where the left interface is immobile and the right interface is moving with 0.01 lattice constants per time step. The position of the interface is indicated with vertical lines at different time-steps.

4. Conclusions and outlook

The connection between phase interface movement, diffusion, partitioning over immobile and mobile interfaces was mathematically examined by starting from the probability of atom movement and connecting to continuum diffusion equations. Simple random walk simulations were conducted to show the operation of the mechanisms in the presence of mobile and immobile phase interface. In future, the activation barriers for atom movement can provide the necessary values for calculation of the probabilities for atom movement near the interfaces, which could then be employed for constructing continuum [19] and atomistic random walk [1] simulations based on the equations provided in this study.

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